

Multiprimes Distribution Within a Given Norms

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Abstract- Prime numbers are infinite therefore it is very difficult to find the primes because they have no sequence in general. Although several mathematicians as worked in this field and given different names of primes like twins primes, thrins primes, mersenne primes and many more. Here we are generating the role of primes in a different manner because fundamental theorem says that every number can be factorized as the product of primes. Our study will be about the pairs of composite numbers which can be factorized as a product of non-repeating primes. With the help of this we are going to develop certain distributions and their applications in the field of cryptography key system.

Keywords— Public key; prime numbers; twins prime; twins (α_r)

I. INTRODUCTION

A positive integer $n > 1$ is called a prime number if its only divisors are either unit or associates; otherwise it is a composite number. 1 is neither prime nor composite number. Prime numbers play a central role in number theory, as any positive integer $n > 1$ can be written uniquely into the following standard prime factorization form:

$$n = p_1^{a_1} \cdot p_2^{a_2} \cdot p_3^{a_3} \cdot \dots \cdot p_r^{a_r}$$

where $p_1 < p_2 < p_3 < \dots < p_r$ are primes and $a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_r$ are positive integers.

Here we are doing the combined study of primes and restricted composites.

II. MULTIPRIMES

Multiprimes is a composite number which can be factorized as a product of non-repeating primes. It is defined as:

$M [P, r] = \{x: x \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and } x = p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_r\}$,
where $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_r$ are primes.

If $n = p_1^{a_1} \cdot p_2^{a_2} \cdot p_3^{a_3} \cdot \dots \cdot p_r^{a_r}$ and at least one $a_i > 1$ then it is called Non-Multiprimes.

III. TWINS PRIME

Twins prime numbers are of the form $n \pm 1$ where both numbers are primes. (3,5), (5,7) and (11,13) are the first three smallest twin prime pairs.

IV. TWINS (α_r) [$T(\alpha_r)$]

Twins (α_r) is an ordered pair in which the first number is the product of smaller twins and the second number is the product of greater twins with $T(\alpha_0) = 1$ and $T(\alpha_i)$ are twins prime. i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} T(\alpha_0) &= 1 \\ T(\alpha_1) &= \{(p_i, q_i) : p_i \text{ and } q_i \text{ are twins prime, } i \in \mathbb{N}\} \\ T(\alpha_2) &= \{(p_i p_j, q_i q_j) : (p_i, q_i) \text{ and } (p_j, q_j) \text{ are twins prime.}\} \\ T(\alpha_3) &= \{(p_i p_j p_k, q_i q_j q_k) : (p_i, q_i), (p_j, q_j) \text{ and } (p_k, q_k) \text{ are twins prime.}\} \end{aligned}$$

V. COMPUTATION OF TWINS (α_r) WITHIN THE GIVEN INTERVAL

A. $T(\alpha_r)$ Within [1, 100]

TABLE 1. $T(\alpha_r)$ WITHIN [1-100] (FOR R = 1, 2, 3, 4)

$T(\alpha_1)$	$T(\alpha_2)$	$T(\alpha_3)$	$T(\alpha_4)$
(3,5)	(15,35)	(165,455)	(2805,8645)
(5,7)	(33,65)	(255,665)	(4785,14105)
(11,13)	(51,95)	(435,1085)	(6765,19565)
(17,19)	(87,155)	(615,1505)	(9735,27755)
(29,31)	(123,215)	(885,2135)	(11715,33215)
(41,43)	(177,305)	(1065,2555)	(7395,20615)
(59,61)	(213,365)	(561,1235)	(10455,28595)

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Mathematical Sciences and their Applications (RASMSA-2014), Kumaun University, Nainital**

(71,73)	(55,91)	(957,2015)	(15045,40565)
	(85,133)	(1353,2795)	(18105,48545)
	(145,217)	(1947,3965)	(17835,46655)
	(205,301)	(2343,4745)	(25665,66185)
	(295,427)	(1479,2945)	(30885,79205)
	(355,511)	(2091,4085)	(36285,91805)
	(187,247)	(3009,5795)	(43665,109865)
	(319,403)	(3621,6935)	(62835,155855)
	(451,559)	(3567,6665)	(16269,38285)
	(649,793)	(5133,9455)	(23001,53105)
	(781,949)	(6177,11315)	(33099,75335)
	(493,589)	(7257,13115)	(39831,90155)
	(697,817)	(8733,15695)	(39237,86645)
	(1003,1159)	(12567,22265)	(56463,122915)
	(1207,1387)	(935,1729)	(67947,147095)
	(1189,1333)	(1595,2821)	(79827,170495)
	(1711,1891)	(2255,3913)	(96063,204035)
	(2059,2263)	(3245,5551)	(138237,289445)
	(2419,2623)	(3905,6643)	(60639,126635)
	(2911,3139)	(2465,4123)	(87261,179645)
	(4189,4453)	(3485,5719)	(105009,214985)
		(5015,8113)	(123369,249185)
		(6035,9709)	(148461,298205)
		(5945,9331)	(213639,423035)
		(8555,13237)	(210453,249185)
		(10295,15841)	(253257,298205)
		(12095,18361)	(364443,690215)
		(14555,21973)	(515247,957395)
		(20945,31171)	(27115,53599)
		(5423,7657)	(38335,74347)
		(7667,10621)	(55165,105469)
		(11033,15067)	(66385,126217)

		(13277,18031)	(65395,121303)
		(13079,17329)	(94105,172081)
		(18821,24583)	(113245,205933)
		(22649,29419)	(133045,238693)
		(26609,34099)	(160105,285649)
		(32021,40807)	(230395,405223)
		(46079,57889)	(101065,177289)
		(20213,25327)	(145435,251503)
		(29087,35929)	(175015,300979)
		(35003,42997)	(205615,348859)
		(41123,49837)	(247435,417487)
		(49487,59641)	(356065,592249)
		(71213,84607)	(350755,569191)
		(70151,81313)	(422095,681163)
		(84419,97309)	(607405,966301)
		(121481,138043)	(858745,1340353)
		(171749,191479)	(222343,329251)
			(319957,467077)
			(385033,558961)
			(452353,647881)
			(544357,775333)
			(783343,1099891)
			(771661,1057069)
			(928609,1265017)
			(1336291,1794559)
			(1889239,2489227)
			(1192567,1544947)
			(1435123,1848871)
			(2065177,2622817)
			(2919733,3638101)
			(4980721,5935849)

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TABLE 2. $T(A_R)$ WITHIN [1-100] (FOR R = 5,6,7,8)

$T(\alpha_5)$	$T(\alpha_6)$	$T(\alpha_7)$	$T(\alpha_8)$
(81345,267995)	(3335145,11523785)	(196773555,702950885)	(13970922405,51315414605)
(115005,371735)	(4799355,16347695)	(236795295,841236305)	
(165495,527345)	(5775495,19563635)	(340754205,1193381735)	
(199155,631085)	(6785295,22675835)	(481755945,1655335955)	
(196185,606515)	(8165355,27136655)	(821818965,2700811295)	
(282315,860405)	(11574915,36997415)	(1270083855,3947339585)	
(339735,1029665)	(13929135,44275595)	(2794184481,7330773515)	
(399135,1193465)	(17888505,54073145)	(4656974135,10263082921)	
(480315,1428245)	(21526845,64710485)		
(691185,2026115)	(39354711,100421555)		
(303195,886445)	(47359059,120176615)		
(436305,1257515)	(65591185,140590177)		
(525045,1504895)	(78931765,168247261)		
(616845,1744295)	(11750145,38496185)		
(742305,2087435)	(20044365,62809565)		
(1068195,2961245)	(30977655,91798595)		
(1052265,2845955)	(68150841,170483105)		
(1266285,3405815)	(113584735,238676347)		
(1822215,4831505)	(28338585,87122945)		
(2576235,6701765)	(43795995,127333535)		
(667029,1646255)	(96351189,236476565)		
(959871,2335385)	(160585315,331067191)		
(1155099,2794805)	(74710815,207754715)		
(1357059,3239405)	(164363793,385830185)		
(1633071,3876665)	(273939655,540162259)		
(2350029,5499455)	(254016771,563905655)		
(2314983,5285345)	(423361285,789467917)		
(2785827,6325085)	(931394827,1466154703)		
(4008873,8972795)			
(5667717,12446135)			

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(3577701,7724735)			
(4305369,9244355)			
(6195531,13114085)			
(8759199,18190505)			
(14942163,29679245)			
(1111715,2304757)			
(1599785,3269539)			
(1925165,3912727)			
(2261765,4535167)			
(2721785,5427331)			
(3916715,7699237)			
(3858305,7399483)			
(4643045,8855119)			
(6681455,12561913)			
(9446195,17424589)			
(5962835,10814629)			
(7175615,12942097)			
(10325885,18359719)			
(14598665,25466707)			
(24903605,41550943)			
(13118237,20084311)			
(15786353,24035323)			
(22716947,34096621)			
(32117063,47295313)			
(54787931,77166037)			
(84672257,112781131)			

From Table I and Table II, we conclude that

- Number of $T(\alpha_0)$ within the interval $[1,100] = 1$
- Number of $T(\alpha_1)$ within the interval $[1,100] = 8$
- Number of $T(\alpha_2)$ within the interval $[1,100] = 28$
- Number of $T(\alpha_3)$ within the interval $[1,100] = 56$
- Number of $T(\alpha_4)$ within the interval $[1,100] = 70$
- Number of $T(\alpha_5)$ within the interval $[1,100] = 56$

Number of $T(\alpha_6)$ within the interval $[1,100] = 28$

Number of $T(\alpha_7)$ within the interval $[1,100] = 8$

Number of $T(\alpha_8)$ within the interval $[1,100] = 1$

The graphical representation of the computation of $T(\alpha_r)$ within the interval $[1,100]$ is shown below:

i.e. the number of $T(\alpha_r)$ within the interval $[1,100] = {}^n C_r$, where n is the number of twins prime within the interval $[1,100]$.

Proceeding in the same way, we can compute $T(\alpha_r)$ within the successive interval $[100,500]$; $[500,2000]$; $[2000,5000]$; $[5000,10000]$; $[10000,20000]$.

FIG. 1. TWINS (α_r) WITHIN THE INTERVAL [1-100]

Fig. 2. TWINS (α_r) WITHIN THE INTERVAL [100-500]

Fig. 4. TWINS (α_r) WITHIN THE INTERVAL 2000-5000]

Fig. 3. TWINS (α_r) WITHIN THE INTERVAL [500-2000]

Fig. 5. TWINS (α_r) WITHIN THE INTERVAL [5000-10000]

Fig. 6. TWINS (α_r) WITHIN THE INTERVAL 10000-20000]

Fig. 7. COMBINED REPRESENTATION OF ALL THE ABOVE $T(\alpha_r)$ WITHIN THE INTERVALS

VI. CONCLUSION

It is clear from the above discussion that the twins distribution is homogeneous about the middle values of twins. Using these results we can generate a secret public key. Breaking such type of system is hardly possible for any unauthorized person.

VII. APPLICATION IN PUBLIC KEY SYSTEMS

For application in the security of ATM password, let the ATM password is "4178". Then we consider, $T(\alpha_8)$ $T(\alpha_7)$ $T(\alpha_1)$ $T(\alpha_4)$.

Since $T(\alpha_r) = {}^nC_r$, so, to find the value of n , add all the digits of ATM password until we get a one digit number i.e. $4178 = 4+1+7+8 = 20 = 2+0 = 2$.

Since the minimum value of sum can be 0 and the digits in the password can be from 0-9 so add 9 to this one digit number 2, we get $2+9 = 11$.

Take $n = 11$ and draw the graph for $T(\alpha_r)$.

Fig. 8. GRAPH OF $T(\alpha_r)$

From the graph it is clear that,

$T(\alpha_4) = {}^{11}C_4 = 330$, $T(\alpha_1) = {}^{11}C_1 = 11$, $T(\alpha_7) = {}^{11}C_7 = 330$,
 $T(\alpha_8) = {}^{11}C_8 = 165$. When n is odd and $r > (n-1)/2$, add 1 to
the value of $T(\alpha_r)$, then we get, $T(\alpha_4) = 330$, $T(\alpha_1) = 11$,
 $T(\alpha_7) = 331$, $T(\alpha_8) = 166$

Hence the encrypted password is “16633111330”

Now to understand which pair of digits should be considered, the decryption key along with encrypted password is “3323” i.e. the encrypted password is “166 331 11 330”. Reverse this code, we get “330 11 331 166”. Now find the value of r corresponding to these values of $T(\alpha_r)$, we get “4178”. This is the original password.

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